

STUDY OF THERMAL PROPERTIES OF POLYETHYLENE MODIFIED WITH FIREFIGHTERS

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Abstract. *By improving the properties of polyethylene, materials obtained from it can be used as substitutes. In the article, the improvement of the thermal properties of polyethylene by modifying its properties was determined using a derivatograph operating in the DTG-60/(SHIMADZU) system and analyzed by the differential thermogravimetric method.*

Keywords: *polyethylene, modification, derivatogram, flame retardant, thermogravimetric analysis, aluminum hydroxide.*

Introduction: The number of fires in Uzbekistan and around the world is increasing every year. Fires can cause many deaths and significant material losses. To prevent such problems, it is important to develop flame-retardant materials and various special additives that reduce flammability. The main flame-retardant systems include halogen compounds, phosphorus, nitrogen, and a number of inorganic compounds.

Inorganic flame retardants include aluminum hydroxide, magnesium hydroxide, ammonium polyphosphate, red phosphorus, etc. These flame retardants account for approximately 50% of world production. [1; 43-46 б].

Currently, there are several hypotheses explaining the reduction in flammability of polymeric materials by using flame retardants, which create a chemical, ionic, or gaseous protective layer.

It should be noted that the above characteristics of fire hazard and flammability are often contradictory, and an improvement in one of these characteristics may be accompanied by a deterioration in the others. In addition, the introduction of additives that reduce the fire hazard of polymeric materials usually leads to a slight deterioration in the physical, mechanical, dielectric and other operational and technological properties, as well as an increase in the cost of the material. Therefore, the task of optimizing the complex of characteristics of the created material in reducing the fire hazard of polymeric materials is set [2].

The use of organic and inorganic modifiers can significantly improve the performance of modified polymer materials. The introduction of a modifier (filler) into polymers leads to the emergence of various interactions at the polymer-modifier interface, which significantly affects the mechanical, physical and chemical, including thermo-oxidative properties of the polymer material [3; 2538-2546 б, 4; 65-68 б,].

Main part: The synthesized compounds were analyzed by differential thermogravimetric method, determined on a derivatograph operating in the DTG-60/(SHIMADZU) system. This method is based on the change in thermal effects of the compounds in the temperature range of 293-793 °C at a temperature increase rate of 2-5 °C/min. The calculation of the effective kinetic indicators of the destruction of the stabilized samples was carried out according to the method of Frimena and Carrolla according to the TGA data. The rate of degradation of the polymer is as follows:

$$dW/dt = (A_0/RH)e^{-E/RT}W^n$$

where RH is the heating rate, W is the polymer size (mass), A₀ is the preexponential factor, n is the reaction composition effect, E is the effective activation energy of polymer thermal destruction. The reaction order is found from the equation of the tangent angle of the slope of the dependence graph in logarithmic coordinates, and the effective activation energy of thermal destruction is determined from the intercept on the ordinate axis [5;16-20, 6; 55,].

First, we will analyze the derivatogram of polyethylene.

Figure 1. Derivatogram of polyethylene. 1- thermogravimetric analysis curve (TGA); 2- differential thermal analysis curve (DTA);

Table 1

Analysis table of derivatogram results of polyethylene

Temperature °C	Time in minutes	Mass (mg)	Lost mass (%)
25,91-281,51	26,85	0,116	3,045
281,51-486,60	47,79	3,795	99,606

The results of these derivatogram studies show that the first mass loss occurs in the 1st decay between 25.91-281.51 °C, in which 3.045% of the original mass is lost, the 2nd decay occurs at 281.51-486.60 °C, in which 99.606% of the mass is lost.

The derivatogram of the sample marked 2023-12-21-1 is presented, which consists of 2 curves. The derivatogram (DTA) curve shows an endothermic effect with three heat absorptions at 121.52°C, 306.45°C and 441.62°C during thermal processes, and no exothermic effect with heat release was observed. Analysis of the thermogravimetric (TGA) curve shows that there are 3 intense decompositions in the TGA curve.

The 1st decomposition occurred in the temperature range of 27.04-188.11°C with a mass loss of 0.051 mg or 0.559%. The 2nd decomposition occurred in the temperature range of 188.11-358.99°C and a mass loss of 2.055 mg or 22.506%. The 3rd decomposition interval occurred in the temperature range 358.99-601.12°C, with a mass loss of 2.385 mg or 26.120%. The total mass loss in the temperature range 27.04-601.12°C was found to be 4.491 mg or 49.185%, which took 59.01 minutes.

Figure 2. Derivatogram of the 2023-12-21-1 branded sample TGA- thermogravimetric analysis curve; DTA - differential thermal analysis curve.

The thermogravimetric analysis curve and differential thermal analysis curve are presented in Table 1 below. From the table, we can see that the highest mass loss occurs in the 3rd decomposition interval, i.e. 26.120% of the mass is lost in this interval.

Based on the results obtained from DTA and TGA analyses, kinetic parameters for different temperature ranges of the process were determined. Its advantage is that the kinetic characteristics of the reactions over the entire temperature range were calculated from a series of measurements and a single sample.

A detailed analysis of the thermogravimetric analysis curve and the differential thermal analysis curve is presented in the following table.

In this TGA analysis, it was determined that 100% of the total mass was thermally decomposed up to a temperature of 601.12°C. (Table 2).

Table 2.

Thermogravimetry (TGA) curve analysis.

Temperature °C	Time in minutes	Mass (mg)	Lost mass (%)
27,04-188,11	16,99	0,051	0,559
188,11–358,99	17,23	2,055	22,506
358,99-601,12	24,79	2,385	26,120

A detailed analysis of the thermogravimetric analysis curve and the differential thermal analysis curve is given in Table 3 below.

Table 3.

Effect of temperature on the weight loss of the 2023-12-21-1 brand sample

№	dw 9.13	1/T	dw/dt	M.g	Mint	T ⁰ +K
1	9.12	0.0026	0.001	0.01	7.08	373
2	9.07	0.0021	0.003	0.06	17.08	473
3	7.99	0.0017	0.042	1.44	27.08	573
4	6.94	0.0014	0.059	2.19	37.1	673

5	4.88	0.0012	0.090	4.25	47.08	773
6	4.65	0.0011	0.078	4.48	57.15.	873
7	4.64	0.0011	0.076	4.49	59.06	893

Oxidative degradation for sample 2023-12-21-1 values of the activation energy of this process are shown for the results. (Table 4).

Table 4.

The results of the thermal oxidation analysis of the 2023-12-21-1 brand sample.

№	dw	9.13	$\ln(W_1/W_2)$	$1/T * 10^{-3}$
1	9.12		0.001	2.6
2	9.07		0.006	2.1
3	7.99		0.133	1.7
4	6.94		0.274	1.4
5	4.88		0.626	1.2
6	4.65		0.674	1.1
7	4.64		0.676	1.1

Thus, on the basis of the experimental data obtained on the kinetics of processes in the temperature range from 300.04 to 874.12 °C, the characteristics of the thermal-oxidative degradation of the 2023-12-21-1 brand sample were studied.

Figure 1 shows a thermogram of pure polyethylene with a TG of 438-440 °C and a 50% mass loss. Figure 2 shows a thermogram of PE composites modified with the sample marked 2023-12-21-1 with a TG of 456-460 °C and a 50% mass loss.

When polyethylene is modified, almost all its properties increase. For example, when the elastic modulus and heat resistance are increased, the impact strength of polymers usually decreases, because these indicators are inversely proportional, and the presence of atomic metal particles contributes to the increase of stiffness and elasticity of the base polymer.

Conclusion: The experimental data obtained indicate that this research direction is promising, since the development of new polymer compounds based on flame retardants and polyethylene will allow expanding the scope of application of basic polyethylene.

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